

HOARD COINS OF KORUKONDA, EAST GODHAVARI DISTRICT, 1981

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The Vishnukundin dynasty was established in 5th and 6th centuries and played an important role in the history of the Deccan including Andhra. Vishnukundin rulers issued so many types of coins for their political, economical development. These are discovered in entire Deccan and Andhra region; places are in Keesara Village, Rangareddy District, Korukonda, East Godavari District, Talukunta Village, Karimnagar District and other places. These coins are preserved in AP State Archaeology and Museums, Hyderabad. Now, we selected one Hoard of coins from Korukonda village, East Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh for this research article.

The earliest of Vishnukundin coins feature the humped bull. The majority of the Vishnukundin coins, however, portray a lion standing right with a twisted and uplifted tail and an open mouth. The lion was the dynastic emblem of the Vishnukundins. In Andhra, Lion type coins only available. Vishnukundins coins were made from ternary alloy consisting of copper, iron and tin, containing about 22% iron, 75.4% copper, 3 % tin. As for the metal of these coins, it is interesting to note that Vishnukundins were the first to have used iron as a core material for their coins, which were coated with copper alloy at the top.

There are 36 coins discovered from Korukonda village and East Godhavari District, Andhra Pradesh in 1981. Now, these coins are preserved in Andhra Pradesh State Museum and Archaeology. These are uninscribed coins of various rulers. Copper or alloyed metal used for making coins.

Obverse: A big Lion facing right with mouth open, tail curled above, left forepaw raised. Crescent above. Some dots seem entire picture.(S.No.2)

Reverse: Vase in two pellets on two slender legs with two curved lines and a lamp stand on either side, in a rayed circle. Another picture in not clear.

Obverse: Lion facing right with mouth open. Double “ya” symbol before the mouth. Remaining picture not clear.(S.N.7)

Reverse: Vase in two pellets on two slender legs with one curved lines and remaining figure same as above. Rayed circle completely seen left side and vase right side.

Obverse: Lion facing right with mouth open. Left forepaw raised and tail curled and double “ya” symbol before the mouth. Remaining picture is not clear. **(S.No.13)**

Reverse: Vase in two pellets on two slender legs with two curved lines and a pellet above and a lamp stand on either side, all in a rayed circle.

Obverse: Lion is facing right with mouth open, tail curled above, and entire figure within a lined circle. Externally decorated with dots. **(S.No.21)**

Reverse: Vase in two pellets on two slender legs with two curved lines and a pellet above and a lamp stand on either side, all in a rayed circle.

Obverse: Lion facing right with mouth open, tail curled above, left forepaw raised and double “ya” symbol before mouth. Crescent above. The entire figure within a lined circle externally decorated with dots. **(S.No.25)**

Reverse: Vase in one pellet on two slender legs with one curved lines and remaining figure same as above. Rayed circle completely seen left side

Most of the coins have same features. Some coins are not clear visible and some coins (S.No. 6, 17, 23, 34) are partially broken. This data helped for the systematic study of the coins and currency system of the Vishnukundins. All the coins in the collection of the museums are without any legend and hence they cannot be ascribed to any individual rulers of this dynasty.

RESULTS

The results are listed in table and histograms

S.NO	SIZE(CMs)	WEIGHT(GMs)
1	2.06	5.4
2	2.04	3.64
3	2.04	4.24
4	2.04	4.24

5	2.06	5.18
6	2.03	3.55
7	2.04	5.19
8	2.07	4.8
9	2.04	4.12
10	2.03	4.85
11	2.04	3.58
12	2.03	3.42
13	2.06	4.5
14	2.04	4.08
15	2.04	3.5
16	2.08	3.84
17	2.08	5.04
18	2.07	3.76
19	2.05	2.93
20	2.06	4.45
21	2.05	5.31
22	2.07	4.11
23	2.08	4.99
24	2.06	4.2
25	2.06	4.85
26	2.06	4.7
27	2.08	5
28	2.05	3.41
29	2.06	5.02
30	2.08	3.9
31	2.03	2.81
32	2.05	3.36
33	2.06	4.17
34	2.06	3.25
35	2.05	4.14
36	2.07	3.1

Discussion

The weights of copper coins ranged between 2.81-5.31 grams. It is obvious that the coins of various denominations were issued. The mean weight of copper coins was 4.18 grams.

CONCLUSION

In entire study told that vishnukundins are not maintained proper currency system and issued coins in different type with various denominations. These coins are very useful to know the political boundaries of the Vishnukundins, and their religious development. Vishnukundins were

confined to the Vengi region, situated between the Godavary in the north and the Krishna in the south, with occasionally extensions beyond these two rivers.

A cultural study of coins from the points of view of religious symbols, iconography, and technological developments would be highly rewarding exercise. The vase or pumakumba one of the eight auspicious symbols is found on the Vishnukundin coins. A large number of animals have been depicted on these coins. In Andhra, the lion and purnakumba symbols are found on the Vishnukundin coins.

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